

STUDIES IN LONG-CHAIN ACIDS. PART V. ON ALEURITIC ACID.

BY P. C. MITTER AND SAILENDRAMOHAN MUKHERJEE

ω -Methoxy-9:10-hexadecenoic acid, intermediate product in the synthesis of aleuritic acid, has been synthesised, starting from ω -methoxyhexyl bromide and 9-methoxy-8 : 9-dibromononyl chloride.

Aleuritic acid is one of the most important constituents of shellac resin obtained by its hydrolysis. Nagel assigned the structure (X) to aleuritic acid based on analytical experiments (*Ber.*, 1927, 60, 605), but the synthesis of this acid has not yet been achieved. Mitter and Dutt (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 673) attempted to synthesise the acid over ω -phenoxy-10-keto hexadecic acid, but without success

Noller and Bannerot (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1563) have synthesised oleic acid by taking advantage of the Boord's reaction (Shoemaker and Boord, *ibid.*, 1931, 53, 1505) for the introduction of a double bond in a carbon chain. We have successfully synthesised ω -methoxy-9 : 10-hexadecenoic acid (VI) following the reactions similar to those adopted by Noller and Bannerot (*loc. cit.*) for the synthesis of oleic acid. Our scheme for the synthesis of aleuritic acid is as follows :—

ω -Methoxyhexyl bromide (I) has been prepared from the corresponding alcohol which in its turn is obtained by the Bouveault reduction of ethyl ω -methoxyhexoate. An attempt has been made to prepare ω -methoxyhexyl alcohol by the action of the Grignard reagent from methoxy propyl bromide on trimethylene chlorohydrin, according to the method of Conant and Kirner (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 232), but unfortunately the desired product could not be obtained satisfactorily. Ethyl ω -hydroxyhexoate is prepared by the oxidation of cyclohexanone (Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 371) with Caro's acid. The hydroxy-ester on treatment with phosphorus tribromide and pyridine (*cf.* Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 723) gives the bromo-ester which with sodium methoxide under specified condition (see experimental) yields the desired ethyl ω -methoxy hexoate in good yield. The reduction of ethyl ω -methoxyhexoate with sodium and ethyl alcohol presents no difficulty provided that the alcohol used is dried over calcium (*cf.* Rydon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 594). ω -Methoxyhexyl alcohol, thus obtained, is converted into the corresponding bromo compound (I) by means of phosphorus tribromide and pyridine. For the preparation of 9-methoxy-8 : 9-dibromononyl chloride (II), we first tried to oxidise aleuritic alcohol by lead tetra-acetate (Criegee, *Ber.*, 1931, 64, 260). On being reduced with sodium and sodium-dried butyl alcohol, ethyl aleuritrate gives a solid tetra-ol in moderate yield but the oxidation with lead tetra-acetate proves to be most unsatisfactory and the yield of the desired product namely ω -hydroxynonyl aldehyde is so poor that the process has been abandoned in favour of the method of Noller and Bannerot (*loc. cit.*) namely the ozonisation of 9 : 10-octadecenyl chloride.

The compound (III), obtained by the reaction between the Grignard reagent from ω -methoxyhexyl bromide and 9-methoxy-8 : 9-dibromononyl

chloride, is not isolated but the crude product is subjected to zinc dust treatment in butyl alcohol (*cf.* Noller and Bannerot, *loc. cit.*). The product (IV), namely ω -methoxy-8 : 9-pentadecenyl chloride, is purified by repeated fractional distillation in *vacuo* and is converted into the corresponding nitrile by treatment with sodium cyanide in alcoholic solution. The crude nitrile is hydrolysed with 20% alcoholic potassium hydroxide. The overall yield of this acid is so very poor that further progress could not be made. Experiments are in hand to prepare large amount of this acid in order to complete the synthesis of aleuritic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl ω -hydroxyhexoate was prepared by the method of Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 371).

Ethyl ω -Bromohexoate.—Phosphorus tribromide (10 c.c.) was added dropwise in the cold to a flask containing ethyl ω -hydroxyhexoate (27 g.), dry benzene (10 c.c.) and a few drops of pyridine. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight and then refluxed on the water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. After cooling, the mixture was diluted with water, extracted with benzene and the benzene layer washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water, dried over calcium chloride and the solvent removed. The residue was distilled at 128-30°/16 mm., yield 23 g. (Found : Br, 35.4. $C_8H_{16}O_2Br$ requires Br, 35.87 per cent).

Ethyl ω -Methoxyhexoate.—To a solution of sodium methoxide (from 3.7 g. sodium and 85 c.c. dry methyl alcohol), chilled in a freezing mixture (-15°), were added ethyl ω -bromohexoate (35 g.) drop by drop. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight and then refluxed for 12 hours when the solution assumed a red colour. The mixture was diluted with water, extracted with ether, the ethereal layer washed and dried ($CaCl_2$) and the solvent removed. The residue on vacuum distillation gave 18 g. of ethyl ω -methoxyhexoate, b.p. 94-95°/15 mm. (Found : C, 61.82; H, 10.46. $C_8H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 62.07; H, 10.34 per cent).

ω -Methoxyhexyl Alcohol.—To a warm solution of ethyl ω -methoxyhexoate (23 g.) in calcium-dried alcohol (275 c.c.) sodium (22 g.) was added all at once. After the initial vigour of the reaction had subsided the mixture was heated on an oil-bath until the whole of sodium went into solution (4 to 5 hours). The contents of the flask were then allowed to attain room temperature, 18 c.c. of water added and the heating under reflux continued for 1 hour. Then further water (130 c.c.) was added and the solution heated for another hour. The solution was then steam-distilled. The residue left after the removal of alcohol was diluted with

water, saturated with sodium chloride and extracted three times with ether, the ethereal extract washed, dried (sodium sulphate), the solvent evaporated and the residue distilled in *vacuo*, when a colourless mobile liquid came over at $112^{\circ}/18$ mm., yield 11 g. (Found : C, 63.2 ; H, 11.9. $C_7H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 63.63 ; H, 12.1 per cent).

ω -Methoxyhexyl Bromide (1).—The above alcohol (6 g.) and pyridine (1.5 c.c.) were added in course of 15 minutes to phosphorus tribromide (4.5 g.) and 1 c.c. pyridine and the mixture well-stirred and maintained at 0° . Stirring was continued for 1 hour and the mixture kept overnight. After the addition of ice-water the product was extracted with ether. The extract was washed with acid and then with aqueous sodium carbonate and water, dried over sodium sulphate, the solvent removed and it was distilled in vacuum, b.p. $98-99^{\circ}/19$ mm., yield 5.5 g. (Found : Br, 41.42. $C_7H_{14}OBr$ requires Br, 41.02 per cent).

Aleurityl Alcohol.—Sodium (12.5 g.) was added all at once to a warm solution of ethyl aleuritate (25 g.) in butyl alcohol (210 c.c.). After the initial vigour subsided, the flask was heated on an oil-bath (180°) until the whole of sodium went into solution (3-4 hours). After cooling water (9 c.c.) was added and refluxing continued for 1 hour. Water (62 c.c.) was then added and the mixture heated for another hour. The contents of the flask were then subjected to steam-distillation until the whole of butyl alcohol was driven off. The residual liquid was then extracted three times with ethyl acetate, the extract dried over sodium sulphate and the solvent removed. The residue on cooling solidified. It was crystallised from petroleum ether ($40^{\circ}-60^{\circ}$), m.p. 56° . (Found : C, 66.22 ; H, 11.57. $C_{16}H_{34}O_6$ requires C, 66.2 ; H, 11.7 per cent).

Oxidation of Aleurityl Alcohol with Lead Tetraacetate.—The above alcohol (10 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (100 c.c.) distilled over chromic acid and the solution was treated at $15-20^{\circ}$ with lead tetra-acetate (33 g.), which was added in portions after which the reaction mixture was heated for 2 hours more at $40-45^{\circ}$. After the lead tetra-acetate was filtered, the filtrate was diluted with water and shaken with ether, the ether solution thoroughly washed and dried over sodium sulphate. The residue after the evaporation of ether was distilled in *vacuo* when only a few drops of ω -hydroxy nonyl aldehyde were obtained, b.p. $102^{\circ}/4$ mm.

ω -Methoxy-8:9-pentadecenyl Chloride (IV).—8:9-Dibromo-9-methoxynonyl chloride (8 g. prepared according to the method of Noller and Bannerot), was diluted with dry ether (20 c.c.). This solution was added drop by drop to the cooled Grignard solution prepared from ω -methoxyhexyl bromide (12 g.) and magnesium (1.5 g.) in 25 c.c. of

dry ether. The mixture was allowed to warm up to room temperature, allowed to stand overnight and then decomposed with ice and ammonium chloride and the product after washing and evaporation of the ether was heated for 1 hour at $60^{\circ}/5$ mm. It was pale yellow in colour.

The above product without further purification was dissolved in dry butyl alcohol (40 c.c.) and refluxed for 10 hours with zinc dust (10 g.). After removal of zinc the solution was washed with hydrochloric acid and water and distilled. After three fractionations 2 g. were obtained, b.p. $198-204^{\circ}/5$ mm. (Found: Cl, 12.23. $C_{11}H_{21}OCl$ requires Cl, 12.93 per cent).

ω-Methoxy-9:10-hexadecenenitrile.—To the solution of the chloro compound (2 g.) in 17 c.c. of 95% alcohol was added sodium cyanide (1 g.) and a pinch of sodium iodide. The mixture was refluxed for 90 hours, poured into water, extracted with ether and the extract washed and dried. The residue left after the removal of the solvent was subjected to the next treatment without further purification.

ω-Methoxy-9:10-hexadecenoic Acid (VI).—The above nitrile was refluxed for 90 hours with alcoholic potassium hydroxide (50 c.c., 20%). The solution was diluted and extracted with ether to remove any unreacted nitrile. The aqueous layer was acidified and extracted with ether, the extract washed and dried over sodium sulphate. After the evaporation of the solvent, the residue was distilled in vacuum when it came over at $194^{\circ}/2$ mm. (Found: C, 71.62; H, 10.8. $C_{17}H_{32}O_2$ requires C, 71.83; H, 11.27 per cent).

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF
SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA.

Received April 20, 1942.